

GEOPHYSICAL EVALUATION OF WATER DRAINAGE AND CONTAINMENT IN A MINE WASTE STORAGE FACILITY: A COMPARATIVE ERT STUDY

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ABSTRACT. Mine waste storage facilities pose significant environmental challenges due to the potential for water infiltration, contamination, and structural instability. Effective monitoring of these facilities is crucial to prevent environmental degradation, optimise waste management, and ensure regulatory compliance. Electrical Resistivity Tomography (ERT) is a widely used geophysical technique for assessing the subsurface conditions, as well as those in mine waste storage facilities, providing valuable insights into water movement, waste containment integrity, and potential failure risks. By deploying an array of electrodes along the surface, ERT generates 2D resistivity profiles that reveal subsurface heterogeneities, which is crucial for making informed decisions about drainage efficiency and waste stability.

Key words: electrical resistivity tomography (ERT), mine waste, drainage.

ГЕОФИЗИЧНА ОЦЕНКА НА ДРЕНАЖА И ЗАДЪРЖАНЕТО НА ВОДА В СЪОРЪЖЕНИЕ ЗА СЪХРАНЕНИЕ НА МИННИ ОТПАДЪЦИ: СРАВНИТЕЛНО ПРОУЧВАНЕ ПО МЕТОДА НА ЕЛЕКТРОТОМОГРАФИЯ

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РЕЗЮМЕ. Съоръженията за съхранение на минни отпадъци могат да поставят значителни екологични предизвикателства поради възможността за дренiranje на замърсени води и структурна нестабилност. Ефективното наблюдение на тези съоръжения е от решаващо значение за предотвратяване екологичните рискове, оптимизиране на управлението на отпадъците и осигуряване на съответствие с нормативните изисквания. Електроотомографията (ERT) е широко използван геофизичен метод за оценка на подповерхностните условия, а също и на съоръжения за съхранение на минни отпадъци, предоставяща ценна информация за наличието на оводнени участъци, целостта на съоръжението и потенциалните рискове от повреда. Чрез разполагане на електроди по повърхността, методът на електроотомографията предоставя 2D профили на разпределението на електричното съпротивление, които разкриват подповерхностни особености на разреза, което е от решаващо значение за вземане на информирани решения относно ефективността и стабилността на съоръженията.

Ключови думи: Електроотомография, минни отпадъци, дренаж.

Introduction

At the current stage, complex geophysical surveys are an essential component of the modern mining industry. In open-pit mining conditions, various challenges often arise that, in some cases, can lead to unforeseen delays or even disrupt the effective operation of a mine. In such situations, the prompt and timely resolution of issues is critical for maintaining the work process and ensuring a safe and healthy working environment.

Over the years, many authors have studied the impact, storage methods, types of tailings, and consequences of mining waste. Tailings consolidation is a critical step in mining waste management. Tailings are a byproduct of mining and mineral processing operations, and they are typically composed of finely ground rock particles, water, and reagents used in the mineral processing. The tailings disposal is a significant environmental and safety concern, as unconsolidated or unstable tailings can result in catastrophic failures and environmental damage (Yankova, 2021; Dimitrov et al., 2023a). Potential problems related to tailings facilities stability are a matter of concern, especially where structural failure might endanger nearby communities and the environment (Arcila et al., 2021). Many experts contend that the tailings storage has always been one of the major challenges, considering that these facilities are difficult to construct and operate (Dimitrov et al., 2023b). A review of the literature on this topic (Lyu et al., 2019) found that there are approximately 3500 tailings storage facilities in the world, of which about 3 fail in a year.

The following research is performed in the Integrated Mine Waste Storage Facility (IMWSF) in the town of Krumovgrad. It is a complex infrastructure designed to safely store waste generated by mining activities. The facility is developed with a

focus on minimising the negative environmental impacts associated with the storage and processing of mine waste. One of the key advantages of this type of mining waste storage facility is the ability to carry out parallel reclamation of different sections, even during the ongoing disposal of tailings (Tomova and Kisyov, 2024).

With the growing scientific and regulatory demands for continuous monitoring of geological and geotechnical processes—such as waste storage, deep excavations, and water resources—electrical resistivity tomography is increasingly being utilised for the timely and efficient tracking of subsurface processes and structural changes in the investigated section. As noted by Kisyov (Tomova & Kisyov, 2024), the use of electrical resistivity tomography (ERT) for studying an integrated mine waste disposal facility provides a non-invasive means of imaging the internal structure of the facility's cells. This method relies on the principle of differing electrical conductivity among the materials composing each cell to generate an image of the facility's structure (Kisyov et al., 2024).

For safety issues, it is reasonable to perform regular monitoring of such facilities. To optimise the design, construction, operation, and eventual closure of a facility, it is essential to consider the specific characteristics of each site—such as its location, disposal methods, management strategies, and long-term closure goals. Achieving this requires a comprehensive assessment during the site selection stage, including evaluation of foundation conditions, land use patterns, seismic risks, and hydrological factors.

Many authors state that geophysical techniques are useful, along with non-invasive, inexpensive and fast-working tools to manage a wide range of geological, engineering and

environmental problems (Hanna and Pfeiffer, 2007; Martinez-Pagán, et al., 2009). Geophysical methods are one of the main ways to collect information about the structure of the subsurface.

Electrical resistivity tomography (ERT) is a key geophysical method used to generate high-resolution images of the upper part of the Earth's crust (Xayavong et al., 2022).

Measurements are usually carried out in a strict sequence of instrument operation and along profile lines. The results are often used in mining, geology, and increasingly in engineering. Without a doubt, one of the most frequently used methods is from the group of Electrical Resistance Methods and this is its most popular modification - electrical resistivity tomography (ERT).

Description of technology

This research was conducted to identify possible flux zones in the integrated waste storage facility using DC resistivity and electrical resistivity tomography (ERT). A shallow, non-destructive geophysical technique – the Electrical Resistivity Tomography (ERT) – was used to delineate the facility cell geometry and thickness of the mine waste. This technique is largely used in such investigations.

The IMWSF is designed as a fully self-draining facility. A system of drains is integrated into the bottom of each cell, directing water into one of two tanks located at the facility's end.

In electrical resistivity tomography (ERT), the measured resistivity values reflect the electrical properties of the subsurface directly beneath the survey line. Data on the physical properties of the target objects and their surrounding environment serve as the primary basis for assessing the applicability of various geophysical methods. This makes the method particularly well-suited for monitoring water-bearing formations, which typically exhibit strong electrical contrasts relative to the surrounding materials.

The measurements were performed using a computer-controlled multielectrode system with many electrodes (96) laid out in a profile at constant intervals (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Equipment used in the field measurements

The data acquisition consisted of 3 ERT lines with 3 m of spacing between electrodes, using a Schlumberger array. This array is well-known for its high signal-to-noise ratio and good vertical resolution. The ERT technique provides detailed information both laterally and vertically along the profile and is the most frequently applied technique in geological and engineering studies.

The registration was carried out using Australian equipment, specifically ZZ Universal 96-Channel Resistivity/IP Meter. The equipment allows measuring the specific electrical resistance of the medium, and is also successfully used for measuring self and induced potentials (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. ZZ Universal 96-Channel Resistivity/IP Meter

One of the major advantages of the equipment is its ability to display data quality in real time, enabling the operator to filter out any noise – such as background, contact, or instrument-related interference – immediately. This feature allows the operator to assess the data on-site and, if a degraded signal is detected, to take prompt action to eliminate the sources of interference, when possible.

Electrical measurements of the lines were processed in a two-stage process. In the first stage – initial data processing – anomalous values caused by environmental and some technical electrical noises were removed. Then, the corrected data was processed and interpreted by RES2DINV software (Loke, 2000; Loke, 2004). As Griffiths & Barker (1993) stated the program determines the 2D resistivity model automatically for the observed data. The 2D model used by the inversion programme consists of several rectangular blocks arranged around the data points in the pseudosection. The size and position of the blocks is automatically generated by the programme using the distribution of the data points (Edwards 1977). The root-mean-squared (RMS) error for each electrical section was obtained as a parameter showing the accuracy of the match between the measured and predicted apparent resistivity values (Ernstson and Kirsch, 2006; Acosta, et al., 2014).

ERT has allowed us to determine both the general geometry of the pond's base and the maximum thickness of the mine tailings. In most of the case studies, the resistivity contrast between the infilling (tailings) and the bedrock is high enough to clearly define the bottom pond boundary (Gómez-Ortiz, et al., 2010). As a result, geophysical methods, such as ERT, are widely applied in the investigation of tailings dams, where effective water drainage is crucial for ensuring structural stability.

As noted by Hasan et al. (2021), the fundamental principle of electrical resistivity tomography is based on the differing electrical conductivities of the rocks composing the investigated section. The electrical conductivity of rocks is influenced by numerous factors, including rock type, porosity, permeability, pore connectivity, temperature, salinity, cation exchange capacity, clay content, and the nature of the pore-filling fluid or water (Hasan et al., 2021).

Geophysical methods, and especially electrical resistivity tomography (ERT), are characterised by high efficiency and accuracy, which allows them to be used to delineate the boundaries of highly saturated areas and, respectively, to mark areas where drainage is difficult or compromised (Xu et al., 2022).

The application of geophysical methods at various stages of construction, drainage, consolidation, and dewatering of the cells in the facility enhances the overall understanding of the facility's operations. This enables informed and timely actions to be taken when necessary.

The constructed electrical resistivity model is modified and adapted to reflect the distribution conditions of the subsurface media specific to the study area. This adaptation is based on:

- general information about the lithology, tectonic, and hydrogeological conditions in the study area.
- data on the specific electrical resistivity of different rock types.
- exploratory drilling data, if available.

Field works are performed with 3 ERT lines measured on the North valley. Their length and descriptions are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Description and length of the lines

Number	Name	Length, m
1	ERT - 1	285
2	ERT - 2	285
3	ERT - 3	285

Fig.3 presents terrain view of the measured lines. They extend from the top almost to the bottom of the facility.

Fig. 3. Terrain distribution of ERT lines

Results and analysis

Results from the terrain measurements are presented as ERT lines which present electrical resistivity distribution along the line.

Variations in electrical resistivity typically correlate with changes in lithology, water saturation, fluid conductivity, porosity, and permeability. These correlations allow the method to be effectively used for mapping geological structures, fractures, groundwater bodies, and features, such as tailings dam walls. The aim of this research is to determine the spatial

distribution and delineation of areas with increased water saturation due to incomplete drainage of the deposited tailing material.

Fig. 4. ERT lines

The obtained ERT profiles (Fig. 4) enabled us to estimate both the vertical variations in the thickness of the mine facility infill and the lateral heterogeneity of the tailing materials, as inferred from the observed changes in resistivity values.

In the majority of the measured geoelectrical sections, the electrical resistivity distribution exhibits a well-defined and smoothly varying character.

The strong resistivity contrast between the tailings and the bedrock is high enough to clearly define the bottom cell boundary. Zones indicating the spatial distribution of environments with increased water saturation — resulting from incomplete drainage of the deposited material — are characterised by relatively low electrical resistivity values across all profiles, typically ranging from 30 to approximately 150 Ωm .

On ERT line - 1, two distinct zones are observed. In the lower part of the profile, near the starting site, significant drying of the terrain is evident, accompanied by relatively high electrical resistivity values. In contrast, the upper part of the profile, exhibits low electrical resistivity values, indicating weak consolidation of the deposited material.

ERT line - 2 is in the central part of the northern slope of the Integrated mine waste facility. As observed, the lower part of the profile, near the starting site, shows significantly higher electrical resistivity values compared to the upper part of the profile, where the newly constructed cells are situated.

ERT line - 3 displays a smooth distribution of the electrical resistivity. The basement is clearly delineated, and the deposited material shows signs of consolidation.

According to the geoelectrical sections obtained in terms of the degree of drainage and respective consolidation of the deposited material, the facility can be divided into 3 main zones: starting areas, middle part, and upper part.

- The *starting areas* of the facility are characterised by distinctly elevated electrical resistivity values, suggesting that the drainage and drying processes in these locations are progressing sufficiently well. The starting site of the North valley currently represents the best-drained areas, where a distinct process of consolidation of the deposited materials has begun.
- The *middle zone* is characterised by effective drainage and a gradual increase in electrical resistivity, which indicates the progressive consolidation of the deposited material.
- The *upper part* of the facility represents the most recently constructed cells, which are typically the most saturated, with the lowest degree of drainage. In this area, the electrical resistivity values are predominantly low, suggesting that the terrain remains poorly consolidated and highly saturated. The bottom and walls of these cells are nearly impossible to trace due to the extent of waterlogging.

Conclusions

The extraction and processing of raw materials inevitably generate significant amounts of waste. Effective and safe storage of mining waste is a critical aspect of the mining industry, forming an essential component of socially responsible practices and a company's commitment to sustainable development. Consequently, the development and implementation of innovative methods for the storage, processing, and monitoring of mining waste are crucial. This process underscores the importance of collaboration with regulators, society, and the scientific community to uphold the highest standards of safety and sustainability. At present, non-invasive and advanced techniques enable monitoring of tailings ponds over time, ensuring the ability to respond promptly, maintain safety, and promote sustainability. These practices are vital for environmental protection, safeguarding human health, and maintaining long-term sustainability in the industry. This kind of studies allows an analysis, long-term monitoring, and assessment of the structural stability and pollution risk.

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